

Article

Speed control of a Direct Current (DC) Engine with proportional correction

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Abstract: In this laboratory report, we are going to explain our experiment findings based on the determination of the **Closed-Loop Transfer function FTBF**, studying our system precision (in closed loop system) and finally we are going to study the influence of the corrector P on the looped system from a performance point of view.

Keywords: Engine Control - PID - Precision - Speed - Stability - Static and Dynamic Gain

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1. Main Goal

From this session, we should be able to :

- Determine the closed loop transfer function.
- Study the accuracy of the closed loop system.
- Study the influence of the P corrector on the closed loop system in terms of performance.

2. principle and How to do method ?

First of all, before starting our **Theoretical** explanation, we should explain the principle of this speed control using the **Electromechanical monitor ERD1000**.

How do this speed control work ?

- At the power interface, a voltage control of the motor will be chosen.
- On the model, the friction coefficient will be neglected but the fluid friction factor will be considered.
- We choose the corrector **PID** with only the proportional action activated.
- The speed sensor shall be the unit transfer coefficient speed sensor.

But what do we mean by the PID regulator .

The **PID regulator** , also called PID corrector (proportional, integral, derivative) is a control system making it possible to improve the performance of a servo - control , that is to say a closed-loop system or process. It is the most widely used regulator in industry where its correction qualities apply to multiple physical quantities.

General Principle

A corrector is a calculation algorithm which delivers a control signal based on the difference between the setpoint and the measurement (the error)

The PID corrector works in three ways:

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- **Proportional action:** the error is multiplied by a gain G ;
- **integral action :** the error is integrated and divided by a gain T_i ;
- **derivative action :** the error is derived and multiplied by a gain T_d .

Here, we present an example of the possible architectures to combine the three effects and this is the most classic one, **Figure 1**

Figure 1. Parallel PID series corrector.

3. Addressing the Issue

In our case, to present the block diagram of the system, we used **Matlab - SIMULINK** to simulate this diagram, see **Figure 2**

4. Theoretical Explanation

1. In this question, we intend to determine the **closed loop transfer function** of the system.

$$G(p) = FTBF = \frac{DirectChannel}{1 + Direct Channel * Feedback channel} \tag{1}$$

$$G(p) = \frac{N(p)}{C(p)} = \frac{\frac{\alpha_1}{1+\tau_1 p} K}{1 + (\frac{\alpha_1}{1+\tau_1 p} K * 1)} \tag{2}$$

So, we get

$$G(p) = \frac{\alpha_1 K}{1 + \tau_1 P + \alpha_1 K} \tag{3}$$

We divide by $(1 + \alpha_1 K)$

$$G(p) = \frac{k \frac{\alpha_1}{1+\alpha_1 K}}{\frac{\tau_1}{1+\alpha_1 K} P} \tag{4}$$

So, we can easily identify K_f and τ_f :

$$K_f = \frac{\alpha_1 K}{1+\alpha_1 K} \text{ and } \tau_f = \frac{\tau_1}{1+k\alpha_1}$$

so, Finally, we can write the Closed-Loop function G using the expression below:

$$G(p) = \frac{K_f}{1 + \tau_f P} \tag{5}$$

2. In this question, we should express the static gain and the time constant as a function of parameter k . After that, we will study the evolution of the two characteristic parameters of the system as a function of k .

$$K_f = \frac{K\alpha_1}{1 + \alpha_1 K} = \frac{\alpha_1 K}{\alpha_1(\frac{1}{\alpha_1} + K)} = \frac{K}{\frac{1}{\alpha_1} + K} + \frac{K}{K(\frac{1}{\alpha_1 K} + 1)} \tag{6}$$

Figure 2. the block diagram of the system

As a result, we get

$$K_f = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\alpha_1 K} + 1} \tag{7}$$

As for τ_f , $\tau_f = \frac{\tau_1}{1 + k\alpha_1}$

Now, we will Study the evolution of the two characteristic parameters of the system as a function of k.

if $K = 0$ then $K_f = 0$ and $\tau_f = \tau_1$

also,

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow +\infty} K_f = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_1 = 0$$

3. So, we can conclude that
 - if K Increases then K_f does, so we have a precise and accurate system response
 - if K Increases then τ_f decreases which means that K_f responds proportionally to K but τ_f has an inversed proportional response toward K , so we will expect a low response Time and the system will have a faster response.
4. Now, are going to predetermine the behaviour of the system in the dynamic mode and to Study the behaviour of a response to a constant step size and then the response to a speed step (ramp).

We Used MATLAB to simulate the two curves shown in Figure 3 and 4

Figure 3. behaviour of a response to a constant step size (Echelon)

Figure 4. Uncompensated system's Closed-Loop Ramp Response (Rampe)

As we can see from Figure 3, the **Static Error** is the difference between the **logarithmic response (shown in blue)** and the **constant set-point step (Horizontal segment)**. However, when we apply a **ramp set-point**, we get a different modeling as shown in Figure 4 which is a **Ramp response** and we can clearly identify the Uncompensated system's Closed-Loop Ramp Response, and here the error is called **Train Error**.

MATLAB Codes used for Plotting the two curves above:

Code for Figure 3

```
fplot(@(x) log(x));  
yline(2.708,'--',{ 'static position error' })  
xlim([0 15]);  
ylim([0 4]);  
yline(3,'-', 'constant setpoint step');  
xlabel('Time (sec)')  
ylabel('Amplitude')  
legend('System Response', 'System Resp Max',  
'Constant set-point step')
```

Code for Figure 4

```
s = tf('s');  
G = ((s+3)*(s+5))/(s*(s+7)*(s+8));  
T = feedback(G,1);  
t = 0:0.1:25;  
u = t;  
[y,t,x] = lsim(T,u,t);  
plot(t,y,'b',t,u,'m')  
xlabel('Time (sec)')  
ylabel('Amplitude')  
title('Input-purple, Output-Blue')  
legend('Input','Output system response');
```

5. In this question, we are going to determine the expression for the **static position and drag error**.

Static Position Error:

$$\epsilon_P = \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \epsilon(t) = C(p) - M(p)$$

Drag Error:

$$\epsilon_P = \lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \epsilon(t) = \lim_{p \rightarrow 0} P\epsilon(p) = \lim_{p \rightarrow 0} P(C(p) - M(p))$$

5. Experiment and Case Study

Static Mode

Below the Table showing our experiment results:

Without Friction Factor

Set-Point (tr/min)	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000
K_2 (V/tr/min)	0.01	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.24
Measurement (tr/min)	886	929	953	966	971	972
ϵ	112	75	38	26	26	25
K_f (10^{-5})	5.27	26.353	52.693	79.018	105.33	126.370

Table 1: Results reported of the first experiment during static mode without friction

From the First Laboratory report of the first session, we have :

$$\alpha = \frac{30K_u}{\Pi K_m} = \frac{30 \cdot 0.87}{\Pi \cdot 43.8 \cdot 10^{-3}} = 189.6778089$$

So, we can calculate K_f for each value in the table 1 using the expression 7

Now, we can plot the two curves $k_f = f(k_2)$ and $\epsilon = f(k_2)$

Figure 5 shows exactly what we have pretended theoretically, we can see that when K_2 increases, K_f does.

From **Figure 6**, we can see that when k_2 Decreases, ϵ does also.

We report below, **Figure 7** showing the behaviour of the **Input, Output and Error response curves** using a constant Step-point of 1000 tr/min and a value of $K_2 = 0.010V/tr/min$.

We report 3 Fixed points in the obtained curve and we will calculate the **response time** t_r and **Time Constant** τ

So, we find:

- $t_r = 0.670$ s
- $\tau = 0.2964$ s

Figure 5. Curve of the Variation of K_f in function of K_2

Figure 6. Curve of the Variation of ϵ in function of K_2

With Friction Factor:

When we apply a friction action, using a value of $K_2 = 0.05V/tr/min$, we get, the curve shown in **Figure 8**, in which we can easily detect the **Oscillation** aspect of it and this is due to the high friction factor we have introduced in the system.

Dynamic Mode

Here we reported the values from the experiment using the dynamic mode, see **Table 2**

Now, we will change the mode of action for the system, so we **choose Speed Ramp response mode**.

We got the curve shown in **Figure 10**, in which we can see the **ramp shape** we have expected, this curve was obtained using **no friction factor** and this is wide clear because there is no a big series and amplitudes of **Oscillations**.

Figure 7. Response curve of a Constant Step-point of 1000 tr/min with a value of $K_2 = 0.01V/tr/min$

Figure 8. Response curve of a constant step-point of 1000 tr/min with a value of $K_2 = 0.05$ using friction at a level of 60 percent

But now, we have increased the Friction behaviour up to 100, see Figure 11 which means that we are operating in a full friction condition and the High oscillating amplitudes show us that the system is under Hard friction.

Set-Point (tr/min)	996	996	996
K_2 (V/tr/min)	0.01	0.15	0.24
Measurement (tr/min)	425	959	970
ϵ	996-425	996	996

Table 2: Results reported of the first experiment during **dynamic** mode

We pretend, now, to Plot the curve of the **Measurement M** in function of the **Step-point** we have used, **Figure 9**

So here we can conclude that even though we apply a constant step-point value, the response of system is decreasing in a remarkable manner.

Figure 9. Curve showing the variation of the Measurements in function of the Constant Step-point values

Figure 10. speed Ramp Response with $K_2 = 0.05$ and no friction

Figure 11. speed Ramp Response with $K_2 = 0.05$ with full friction

6. Conclusion

From this session and after understanding the mechanism of action and principles of the Speed control of the DC Engine with proportional correction, we are now able to **determine the closed loop transfer function, study the accuracy of the closed loop system and finally study the influence of the P corrector on the closed loop system in terms of performance.**

Author Contributions: LABIDI Aymen, please turn to my [Research gate](#) and [Linkedin](#) for the term explanation and more scientific papers.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this article:

- K_m the torque constant of the motor.
- R the armature resistance of the motor
- j moment of inertia
- K_u the transfer coefficient of the power influence.

Appendix G Other sources

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